

Stability of Uranium (VI) and Zirconium (IV) Complexes with Multidentate Ligands

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Earlier investigators have reported many polydentate ligands and their proton-ligand as well as metal-ligand stability constants^{1,2}. Recently Trivedi *et al* reported the synthesis and chelating tendencies of N,N'-ethylenediamine-disuccinic acid (EDDS)³ and N,N'-ethylenediamine-bis (α -glutaric acid) (EDG)⁴ with bivalent metal ions. The present investigation deals with the composition and the stabilities of uranium (VI) and zirconium (IV) complexes of EDDS and EDG.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis and protonation constants of EDDS and EDG have been discussed previously^{3,4}.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titrations of Uranium (VI) and Zirconium (IV) chelates of EDDS.
Curve A—20 ml. of *M*/50 EDDS.
Curve B—20 ml. of *M*/50 EDDS and 10 ml. of *M*/50 Uranium (VI)
Curve C—20 ml. of *M*/50 EDDS and 10 ml. of *M*/50 Zirconium (IV).

1. A. Yingst and A. E. Martell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 6927.
2. T. A. Bohigian, Jr. and A. E. Martell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 832.
3. O. P. Sunar, Ph.D. Thesis, Jodhpur University, 1971.
4. C. P. Trivedi, O. P. Sunar and Surekha Tak, *J. Inorg. nuclear Chem.* (in press).

AnalaR B.D.H. reagents, uranyl nitrate, zirconium oxychloride, sodium hydroxide, potassium nitrate etc. were used.

pH measurements were made with a Cambridge (Bench type) pH meter using glass and calomel electrodes at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. The measurements were checked before and after the titration with standard buffers.

The potentiometric titrations were carried out for metal to ligand molar ratio 1 : 2 and are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 for EDDS and EDG respectively.

Fig. 2. Potentiometric titrations of Uranium (VI) and Zirconium (IV) chelates of EDG.

Curve A—20 ml. of $M/50$ EDG.

Curve B—20 ml. of $M/50$ EDG and 10 ml. of $M/50$ Uranium (VI)

Curve C—20 ml. of $M/50$ EDG and 10 ml. of $M/50$ Zirconium (IV).

Total volume in all the cases was kept 100 ml. The ionic strength was maintained 0.1 with respect to potassium nitrate. The mixtures were titrated with standard sodium hydroxide solution (1.0 M).

Proton-ligand stability constants for EDDS and EDG were calculated by Bjerrum's⁵ and Irving and Rossotti⁶ methods and have been discussed in the previous communications.

The metal chelate stability constants were determined by Bjerrum's method and the computational methods described by Irving and Rossotti⁷ were employed to determine the formation constants for $UO_2(VI)$ and $ZrO(IV)$ complexes, shown in Table 1.

5. J. Bjerrum, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Sons, Copenhagen, 1957.

6. H. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.

7. H. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3897.

TABLE 1

Formation constants of $UO_2(VI)$ and $ZrO(VI)$ complexes of EDDS and EDG

System	Method	$\log K_1$
$UO_2(VI)$ —EDDS	a	10.60
	b	10.58
$ZrO(IV)$ —EDDS	a	11.20
	b	11.11
$UO_2(VI)$ —EDG	a	12.55
	b	12.40
$ZrO(IV)$ —EDG	a	11.80
	b	11.85

a = Extension of Bjerrum's method.

b = direct calculation method

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The potentiometric titration curves of EDDS and EDG are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. Two protons per ligand molecule dissociate between $\alpha = 0$ and $\alpha = 2$ (where $\alpha =$ moles of base added per mole of ligand present). At higher pH two more protons dissociate between $\alpha = 2$ and $\alpha = 4$. The four protonation constants obtained of EDDS and EDG are 3.25, 4.0, 8.5, 9.4 and 3.75, 4.85, 8.93, 9.75 respectively.

Fig. 3. Formation curves of Metal Ligand Systems.

A—EDDS-Uranium (VI) system.

B—EDDS-Zirconium (IV) system.

C—EDG-Uranium (VI) system.

D—EDG-Zirconium (VI) system.

Low-pH EDDS complexes : The 1 : 2 EDDS curves with $\text{UO}_2(\text{VI})$ and $\text{ZrO}(\text{IV})$ are shown in Fig. 1. The complex equilibria may be represented by

The curves of both the divalent metal ions have a large buffer region from $a = 0$ to $a = 3$ [in case of $\text{ZrO}(\text{IV})$] and $a = 0$ to $a = 3.25$ [in case of $\text{UO}_2(\text{VI})$]. Beyond $\text{pH } 4$ the complexes hydrolyse and the metal hydroxides precipitate in both the cases. The stability constant values calculated from formation curves (Fig. 3) are shown in Table 1.

EDG—Complexes : The 1 : 2 EDG curves with $\text{UO}_2(\text{VI})$ and $\text{ZrO}(\text{IV})$ are shown in Fig. 2. The complex equilibria may be represented by equations (1) and (2). The nature of the equilibria in EDG system is similar to that of EDDS. The complexes formed with EDG are having higher $\log K$ values. Beyond $\text{pH } 4$ these complexes hydrolyse forming their metal hydroxides.

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